

BADIIY ASAR MATNI USTIDA ISHLASHNING O'ZIGA XOSLIGI**Ne'matova Gulnoza Normurodovna**

Buxoro davlat universitetining Pedagogika instituti talabasi

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6589425>

ANNOTATSIYA: Ushbu maqolada umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablarida badiiy asarlar tahlili yuzasidan matn ustida olib boriladigan ishlar o'quvchilarning o'qish va adabiyot darslarida o'zlashtiradigan bilimlari, ko'nikma va malakalari xususida so'z yuritiladi. Xususan, sharhli o'qish, izohli o'qish, adabiy o'qish, badiiy o'qish, ifodali o'qish usullarining pedagogik imkoniyatlari yoritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: badiiy matn, adabiy-estetik tahlil, sharhli o'qish, izohli o'qish, adabiy o'qish, badiiy o'qish, ifodali o'qish, badiiy ijod qonuniyatlari, adabiyotshunoslik, didaktika, kompetensiya, taqqoslash.

O'quvchilarni badiiy asar matni ustida ishlashga o'rgatish ularda adabiy-estetik tahlil malakasini shakllantirish orqali ta'lim-tarbiya berishni nazarda tutadi. Badiiy asar tahlili yozuvchining o'sha asarni yaratish jarayonidagi ijodiy yo'lini qayta bosib o'tish, muallif fikrlari, hissiyoti vaxulosalariga sherik bo'lish, ayni paytda uning yutuqlaridan ruhlanish, kamchiliklariga tanqidiy munosabat bildirishdir.

Tahlil asarni nafaqat tushunish, balki o'zlashtirish orqali ma'naviy-axloqiy barkamollikka erishishga qaratilgan faoliyatdir. Uni ba'zi olimlar, masalan, A.Zunnunov badiiy asarni o'zlashtirish asosi deb bilsa, ayrimolimlar, xususan, M.Mirqosimova adabiy matnning badiiy xususiyatlarini o'rganish usuli degan fikrni ilgari suradi.

O'quvchi mutolaa chog'ida asar mazmuni bilan tanishsa, tahlil paytidapoetikasiga murojaat qiladi. Mutolaa hissiyotni boyitib, aqlni peshlasa, tahlil matn tizimidagi ma'noni chuqur o'rganishga yordam beradi. O'quvchi tahlil vositasida konkret asarni o'rganibgina qolmasdan, adabiyotshunoslik, mantiq, tilshunoslik, didaktika, san'at, falsafa kabi turli fanlarning badiiy ijodga bog'liq qonuniyatlari bilan ham tanishadi. Bunga erishishda o'qituvchining quyidagi masalalarni hal etishi nazarda tutiladi:

1. Tahlilning maqsadi va mazmunini aniqlash.
2. Ishni tashkil qilish (asar tahlilining darslar bo'yicha taqsimoti, topshiriqlar

tizimini ishlab chiqish).

3. Asarning qanday metodlar asosida o'rganilishini, o'quvchilar egallaydigan malaka va kompetensiyalar doirasini belgilash.

Adabiy-estetik tahlil har bir asarning janriy xususiyatlari, o'quvchilaryoshi, bilimi va egallagan malakalariga ko'ra o'ziga xoslik kasb etadi. Masalan, quyi sinflarda topishmoq predmet, voqea-hodisalar o'rtasidagi o'xshashlikni taqqoslash orqali o'zlashtirilsa, maqollar mazmuni hayotiy misollarvositasida sharhlangandagina tushunarli bo'ladi. Chunki kichik yoshdagi bolalar voqealar oqimiga, sarguzashtlarga ishqiboz bo'lsa, katta yoshlilar qahramonlarning ruhiy olami, ichki dunyosiga qiziqadilar. Asar voqealarini tahlillash orqali tarbiyalash 5-6-sinflarda davom etadi. Chunki bu yoshdagi o'quvchilar oqni oq, qorani qora, yaxshini yaxshi, yomonni yomon tarzida konkret tushunadilar, ammo insonning murakkab ichki dunyosi ular uchun mavhumligicha qolaveradi. Sherning botirligi-yu, tulkining ayyorligi, quyoning qo'rqqoligi-yu, itning vafodorligi ularning tajribasidan yaxshi ma'lum. Hayvonlarga xos bunday sifatlar ertak va masal qahramonlarining xatti-harakatlarida, nutqlarida yorqin aks etgan. Lekin ular o'z holicha tasvirlanmaydi, balki boshqaqahramonlar o'rtasida kechadigan ziddiyatlarni anglashga yordam beradi.

O'quvchilarda adabiy tahlil malakasini shakllantirish badiiy matn ustida ishlashning turli shakl va metodlaridan foydalanishni shart qilib qo'yadi. Masalan, ilk tahliliy ko'nikmalar boshlang'ich sinfnig o'qish va ona tili darslarida matn mazmuni yuzasidan savol-javob asosida, shuningdek, to'liq, qisqartirib, ijodiy va shaxsini o'zgartirib hikoyalash vositasida hosilqilinadi. Natijada o'quvchilar matn zaminidagi yetakchi ma'noni aniqlash, asar nafosatini his etish malakasini egallaydilar. O'rta va yuqori sinflarda esa matn ustida ishlashda insho, referat, bayon, taqriz, ma'ruza matnini tayyorlash kabi tsh turlari keng qo'llaniladi.

Badiiy asarlar janr xususiyatlari va dastur talablariga ko'ra sinfda o'qituvchi nazorati ostida, uyda mustaqil tarzda o'qiladi. Sinfda ovoz chiqarib, ovoz chiqarmay ichda, jo'r bo'lib, sharhli, ifodali, adabiy-badiiy o'qish usullarida mutolaa qilinadi. Quyida ularning ayrimlariga to'xtalamiz:

Sharhli o'qish. Sharhli o'qish tarixiy-memuar, ayrim hollarda zamonaviy mavzudagi asarlar mazmunini o'zlashtirishni taqozo etadi. Sharhli o'qish lug'atustida ishlashni anglatmaydi, balki asardagi obrazli ifodalar, maqol va matallar mazmunini sharhlash, tarixiy-afsonaviy, xayoliy-

fantastik timsollar haqida ma'lumotlar berish, izohlash kabi murakkab masalalarni qamrab oladi. Masalan, Abdulla Oripovning "O'zbekiston" (5-sinf) qasidasidagi "Ikki yarim asr dunyoni zir qaqshatdi oqsoq jahongir", "osmon ilmi tug'ilgan ilk bor Ko'ragoniy jadvallarida" misralari sharhlanmasa, mazkur she'rda tilga olingan Beruniy, Chingizxon, Jaloliddin Manguberdi, Sobir Rahimov, Habib Abdullayev kabi tarixiy shaxslar yoxud Erkin Vohidovning "O'zbekim" (6-sinf) qasidasida keltirilgan Afrosiyob, O'rxun xati, Sarbador, Zardusht, Buddha atamaları to'g'risida ma'lumot berilmasa, o'quvchilar o'sha asarlarning mazmunini tushunib yetmaydilar.

Adabiy o'qish. Adabiy asarning badiiy-estetik mohiyati undagiqahramonlar, sahnalar, tabiat tasvirlari, dialoglar va boshqa turli komponentlarning murakkab tartibini o'rganish, sharhlash orqali o'zlashtiriladi. "Badiiy asarni grammatik va poetik qonun-qoidalarga rioya qilib o'qish adabiy o'qish deyiladi. Adabiy o'qishning asosiy vazifasi biror asarning poetik va badiiy xususiyatlarini ochib berishdan iborat" (2, 52). Bu esa adabiy o'qishning metodik xarakter kasb etishini ko'rsatadi. Badiiy matn ustida ishlash jarayonida o'qituvchining vazifasi asarning poetik mazmunini tahlil qilish, mavzusi va tasvir predmetini tushuntirish, qalamga olingan hayot voqeligiga muallif munosabatini aniqlashdan iborat.

Bu vazifani amalga oshirishda ifodali o'qish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Shunga ko'ra, o'qishning bu turini asar ma'no-mazmunini hissiyot va fikr uyg'unlashgan jonli nutq orqali o'quvchiga yetkazish usuli deyish mumkin.

Badiiy asarni ifodali o'qishda uning o'ziga xos ichki janriy xususiyatlari va muallif uslubini inobatga olish talab etiladi. A.Qahhorning "Bemor" hikoyasi bilan Usmon Nosirning "Yur, tog'larga chiqaylik" she'rini, Muqimiyning "Tanobchilar" satirik asari bilan O'tkir Hoshimovning "Urushning so'nggi qurboni" hikoyasini yoki Alisher Navoiyning falsafiy g'azallari bilan Hamid Olimjon hamda G'afur G'ulomning ko'tarinki xarakterdagi hikmatlari o'qilishi jihatidan o'zaro farqlanadi.

Dramatik asarlar sahnaga qo'yishga mo'ljallab yaratilgani va faqat aktyorlar ijrosidagina o'zining estetik, tarbiyaviy vazifasini to'la bajargani, nasriy asarlar tabiatan yakka tartibda o'qishni taqozo etgani kabi, she'riy asarlar ifodali o'qilgandagina yurakdan his qilinadi. Demak, badiiy asarlar tadqiqi va tahlilida ham turli usullardan foydalaniladi. Ammo bunday usullarning birini she'riyat, ikkinchisini nasr, uchinchisini dramaturgiya uchun qat'iy chegaralab bo'lmaganidek,

jamiki asarlarni faqat bir xil shakl va mazmunda, yagona nutqtai nazar asosidp o'rganish mumkin emas.

She'riy asarlar tahlili ifodali o'qishsiz mukammal bo'lmaydi. Binobarin ifodali o'qish tahlil vositasi hamdir. U ko'p hollarda batafsil izohlashdan afzal turadi va o'quvchilarni badiiy asar matni bilan tanishtirishning birlamchi amaliy metodi hisoblanadi. O'zbek adabiyoti ilmigakatta hissa qo'shgan Elbek va atoqli shoir, zukko she'rshunos Maqsud Shayxzodaning lirik she'riyat ma'nosida "yurak she'ri" va "rubobiy she'r" iboralarini ishlatishi bejiz emas.

Umumta'lim maktablari va akademik litsey hamda kasb-hunar kollejlari adabiyot dasturlaridan o'rin olgan asarlarning katta qismi she'riyat namunalari ekani uning adabiyotimiz tarixidagi mavqei, tarixiy taraqqiyoti tufaylidir. Afsuski, dasturlarda she'r matni, xususan, poetikasi ustida ishlashga juda kam e'tibor beriladi. She'riy matnlar so'ngida ilova qilingansavol-topshiriqlarning aksariyatida she'rni yodlash, undagi o'xshatish, sifatlash, jonlantirishlarni topish va belgilash so'ralgan, xolos. Masalan, A.Oripovning "Iqboli buyuksan", Quadrat Hikmatning "Qish to'zg'itar momiq par", T.Adashboyevning "Qish" kabi ko'plab she'rlari yuzasidan tuzilgan savol-topshiriqlarni bunga misol qilib keltirish mumkin.

"Sir emas, she'riy asar tahlili nasriy yoki dramatik asarlarga nisbatan shoirning ichki kechinmalari bilan bog'liqligi tufayli qiyinchilik tug'diradi".

Asarning badiiy ifodalariga doir tahlil o'quvchilarning nutq madaniyatini egallashlarini ta'minlaydi. Shuning uchun ham ayni maqsadga qaratilgan topshiriqlar tizimli usulda amalga oshirishni taqozo qiladi. Masalan:

1. Kuzbor Malikning Malika Oychechakka ko'rsatgan ehtiromlariniifodalagan so'z va iboralarni aniqlab, lug'at daftaringizga yozing va taqdimotgachiqing (*ehtirom ila bosh egdi, tiz cho'kdi, buyuring, sadoqat ila, "Siz buyuk Xorazmshoh rafiqasi, men qulingizman, e'tirozga og'iz juftlamoqchi bo'ldi, bosh ustiga, ta'zim ila*).

2. Malika Oychechakning Kuzborga ko'rsatgan ehtiromini ifodalovchi so'z va iboralarni aniqlab, lug'at daftaringizga yozing va taqdimotga chiqing (*yonidanjoy ko'rsatdi, og'a, o'tiring, minnatdorchilik bilan unga qaradi, uni yuz-xotirqilmang*).

3. Malika Oychechakning onalik tilaklarini ifodalovchi so'z va iboralarni aniqlab, lug'at daftaringizga yozing va taqdimotga chiqing (*injiq- tantiq shahzoda bo'lmasin, chinakam*

bahodir yigit bo'lsin, alp yigit bo'lsin, zehni o'tkir, Jaloliddin valiahd, bugundan shogirdingiz, o'quvchingiz.

Xulosa qilganda, badiiy asarni o'qish turlari undagi har bir so'z, ibora va jumlaning qiroat bilan, to'g'ri, ravon o'qishgina emas, balki matnning umumiyruhiga kirib, tushunib o'qishni ham anglatadi, asarning janriy xususiyatlaridan tashqari, o'ziga xos ichki tuzilishi va ruhiyatini hisobga olishni ham taqozo etadi. Bunga erishish uchun o'quvchilarni matn ustida jiddiyishlashga o'rgatish zarur.

Ушбу мақолада ўқув луғатларининг умумий луғатлардан нафақат ҳажми, балки ундаги сўзларнинг танланиш мезонлари, луғат қисмларининг таркиби, жойлашуви – мегаструктураси билан ҳам фарқланиши, синоним ўқув луғатлар луғат мақоласи таркибида лексикографик пометалар (турли қисқартмалар, белгилар)га кам ўрин берилганлиги муҳокама қилинади.¹

This article is dedicated to the research of Adjusted meanings of Moral-spiritual concept defining units in the Uzbek language. And also analyzed the semantic analysis of grammatical shape lexemes of specialized meaning and provide a corresponding recommendation for lexicographical practice in the Uzbek language is one of the actual challenges of linguistics as today's challenge.²

Корпус лингвистикасида семантик разметка, унинг теглар тизими, тег категориялари, семантик теглаш муаммолари, кўпмаънолик ва омонимлик муаммосини ечиш масаласига оид қатор тадқиқотлар вужудга келган.³

The article discusses the research methods of Uzbek language syntax. In Uzbek linguistics, syntactic phenomena have been studied in detail since the 1930s, and several syntactic theories have emerged in this regard.⁴

¹ Гуландом Мирханова. (2022). СИНОНИМ СЎЗЛАР ЎҚУВ ЛУФАТИНИНГ УМУМИЙ ТУЗИЛИШИ. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal*, 1(2), 172–178. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/90>

² Gulbahor, T. (2016). Adjusted Meanings of Moral-Spiritual Concept Defining Units. *ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association-Institute for English Language and American Studies*, 5(7), 40-45.

³ Ахмедова, Д. (2020). Семантик разметка тизимида тег гуруҳлари. *Oriental Art and Culture*, (III), 440-444.

⁴ Ergashevna, Y. N. (2021). ON METHODS OF RESEARCH OF UZBEK LANGUAGE SYNTAX. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(11), 22-28.

The article examines the first dictionary in the Turkish language Mahmud Kashgaris “Devonu lugotit turk” in terms of a dictionary in accordance with the traditions of world lexicography and argues that it is the first appearance of modern complex dictionaries in the Turkish (Uzbek) language.⁵

Now studying scientific heritage, socio-political activities and acquaintance youth charity of our above-stated ancestors is considered one of the main urgent objectives of the modern intellectuals.⁶

This article covers the main place of small business and business in today's market economy. Including scientifically analyzed the development of small business and business, and the legal basis, at this time financially support small business and business, the latter is amended and the rules for this branch of national legislation are added.⁷

Мамлакатимиз тараққиётининг янги босқичида жамият ҳаётининг асосий негизи бўлмиш оилалар барқарор муҳитини мустаҳкамлаш ва бу масалаларда хотин-қизларнинг ўрни ва аҳамияти ошириш долзарб аҳамият касб этмоқда. Юртимиз аҳолисининг тенг ярмига яқинроғини ташкил этадиган хотин-қизлар жамиятнинг барча соҳаларида самарали фаолият юритмоқда.⁸

In this article are given the importance, role, types of the family in modern society. Its development from ancient times till present is widely described in this article.⁹

The widespread introduction of new pedagogical technologies in teaching students of higher educational institutions and the effective use of innovative technologies are the main support for improving the quality of education.¹⁰

⁵ Bakhridinova, B. M. (2020). “DEVONU LUGOTIT TURK” AS A FIRST VIEW OF MODERN COMPLEX EDUCATIONAL DICTIONARIES. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (4), 981-985.

⁶ Tolibjonovich, M. T. (2021). EASTERN RENAISSANCE AND ITS CULTURAL HERITAGE: THE VIEW OF FOREIGN RESEARCHERS. *ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions*, 2(05), 211-215.

⁷ Tolibjonovich, Madumarov T., and Gulomjonov O. R. Ogli. "Lombard Microcredit Organization Its Concept and Its Importance Today." *JournalNX*, vol. 6, no. 10, 2020, pp. 109-111.

⁸ Мадумарова Зиёдахон. (2022). ЯНГИЛАНАЁТГАН ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА ГЕНДЕР МУАММОЛАРИНИ БАРТАРАФ ЭТИШДА АХЛОҚИЙ ҚАДРИЯТЛАРИНИНГ ЎРНИ. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6569712>

⁹ Nasriddinovich, A. A. (2020). THE FEATURES OF APPEARING FAMILY IN MODERN SOCIETY. *European science review*, (3-4), 69-72.

¹⁰ Jamoliddinovich, U. B. (2022). FUNDAMENTALS OF EDUCATION QUALITY IN HIGHER EDUCATION. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(01), 149-151.

The article describes in detail the basics of translation theory, the object of research, and the methods of analysis of translation theory. Opinions on the importance of translation among different peoples, the concept of translation, and its types are discussed. However, various examples of translation types are given.¹¹

The aim of the present study was to determine whether an association exists between the duration of menopause and the age of menopause onset, and the differences in bone mineral density (BMD) in postmenopausal women.¹²

This article analyzes how Somerset Maugham's short story "A Friend in Need" skillfully reflects the power and value of true friendship using ethical concepts such as goodness, kindness, justice, and compassion, which are sacred to each of us.¹³

The article considers the correlation of the real facts and imagination in "Tamburlaine the Great" by Christopher Marlowe.¹⁴

This article discusses an attitude to women in the past and the interpretation of the image of women in the works of some writers.¹⁵

В современном обществе все более возрастает роль иностранных языков. Знание иностранного языка дает молодежи возможность приобщиться к мировой культуре, использовать в своей деятельности потенциал обширных ресурсов глобальной сети Интернет, а также работать с информационными и коммуникационными технологиями и мультимедийными средствами обучения.¹⁶

¹¹ Gafurovna, R. Z. (2021). Translation Theory: Object of Research and Methods of Analysis. *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies*, 24(2), 35-40.

¹² Najmutdinova, D. K., Nurmukhamedova, L. S., Alieva, D. A., Maksudova, D. S., & Nosirova, Z. A. (2016). Study of the effects of the age at menopause and duration of menopause on bone mineral density in postmenopausal women in Uzbekistan. *International Journal of Biomedicine*, 6(1), 38-40.

¹³ Pulatova Sabina. (2022). THE REVELATION OF VIRTUE THROUGH EVIL IN THE SHORT STORY "A FRIEND IN NEED" BY WILLIAM SOMERSET MAUGHAM. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnali*, 1(2), 240-244. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/100>

¹⁴ Temirovna, M. P. (2021). THE CORRELATION OF HISTORICAL TRUTH AND IMAGINATION IN CHRISTOPHER MARLOWE'S TRAGEDY "TAMBURLAINE THE GREAT". *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 2(12), 455-457.

¹⁵ Muradovich, R. M. (2021). The Image of a Woman in The Work of Uzbek Writers. *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 3, 7-12.

¹⁶ Махмурова, М., Абдуллаева, Л. С., & Самадова, С. А. Современные методы преподавания иностранных языков. Коммуникативный метод. *Наука. Мысль*, 6, 72-76.

This article deals with the heroes of the novel “Between Two Doors”, one of the most popular works of modern Uzbek literature. There is a comprehensive analysis of the female image. A special place in the work of Utkir Khashimov is occupied by the novel “Between Two Doors”. The writer is concerned not only with the pressing social issues of today, but with eternal moral problems. In particular, by calling “Between Two Doors”, the writer means the path of person, which he walked from birth to death.¹⁷

Har bir millat madaniyatida kasallik nomlarini ifodalovchi qarashlar mavjud bo’lib ular shu xalq dunyoqarashini, dinini, urf-odatlarini, turmush tarzini va tarixini o’zida mujassamlashtiradi. Xususan, o’zbek va ingliz xalqi amaliy nutqida rak, sil, vabo kabi xavfli kasalliklar nomi qadimda tabulashtirilgan, bunga tarixiy sabablar mavjud. Hozirgi kunda ularning davosi topilgan bo’lsada, xalqimiz “yomon xastalik”, “og’ir dard”, “yomon kasallik” kabi birikmalarni qo’llash bilan kifoyalanadi.¹⁸

Badiiy adabiyotning qamrov darajasi keng sanaladi. Zero undagi janrlarning har biri insonning kamoloti uchun xizmat qiladi.¹⁹

В данной статье сопоставление диккенсовской концепции детства и концепции детства в произведениях Достоевского.²⁰

В настоящее время глобальной социальной опасностью является угроза обнищания населения. Безработица, экономическая и социальная нестабильность, несбыточность надежд, крушение планов интенсифицируют процесс маргинализация населения.²¹

The relevance of speech and culture in the present day is considered important in linguistics and its areas of study are becoming more and more comprehensive day by day. This article will highlight the important aspects of the study of culture and national characteristics in the study of

¹⁷ Turaeva, K., & Zarinabonu, A. (2022). Interpretation Of Woman Image in Modern Uzbek Literature (Based on Utkir Khashimov’s Book “Between Two Doors”). *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 4, 42-44.

¹⁸ Baxronova Matluba. (2022). RUHIY KASALLIKLARNING INGLIZ ADABIYOTIDA BERILISHI. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6509637>

¹⁹ Oripova Kamola. (2022). O’ZBEK VA FRANSUZ TILLARIDAGI MAQOLLARDA JON KONSEPTINING IFODALANISHI. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnali*, 1(3), 398–408. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/209>

²⁰ Тухтаева, Ф. И., & Хамроева, Ш. Ш. (2019). Сопоставление диккенсовской концепции детства и концепции детства в произведениях Достоевского. *Мировая наука*, (5), 709-713.

²¹ Суяров, З. Э. (2021). СОЦИАЛЬНО-ФИЛОСОФСКОЕ ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ БЕДНОСТИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(12), 1175-1182.

modern units of oral speech. Currently, English is widely spoken in the world community. It is the language of Advanced Science and technology, trade and cultural relations, trade and business.²²

The article is dedicated to the description of Uzbek national children's clothes of the past centuries and its modern implementation. Article describes types of clothes, its designation and modern usage.²³

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR:

1. Гуландом Мирханова. (2022). СИНОНИМ СЎЗЛАР ЎҚУВ ЛУФАТИНИНГ УМУМИЙ ТУЗИЛИШИ. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal*, 1(2), 172-178. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/90>
2. Gulbahor, T. (2016). Adjusted Meanings of Moral-Spiritual Concept Defining Units. *ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association-Institute for English Language and American Studies*, 5(7), 40-45.
3. Ахмедова, Д. (2020). Семантик разметка тизимида тег гуруҳлари. *Oriental Art and Culture*, (III), 440-444.
4. Ergashevna, Y. N. (2021). ON METHODS OF RESEARCH OF UZBEK LANGUAGE SYNTAX. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(11), 22-28.
5. Bakhrididina, B. M. (2020). "DEVONU LUGOTIT TURK" AS A FIRST VIEW OF MODERN COMPLEX EDUCATIONAL DICTIONARIES. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (4), 981-985.
6. Tolibjonovich, M. T. (2021). EASTERN RENAISSANCE AND ITS CULTURAL HERITAGE: THE VIEW OF FOREIGN RESEARCHERS. *ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions*, 2(05), 211-215.
7. Tolibjonovich, Madumarov T., and Gulomjonov O. R. Ogli. "Lombard Microcredit Organization Its Concept and Its Importance Today." *JournalNX*, vol. 6, no. 10, 2020, pp. 109-111.

²² NARZIYEVA, I. Z. (2021, March). COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE CULTURAL AND NATIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF MODERN UNITS OF ORAL SPEECH (based on Uzbek and English language materials). In *E-Conference Globe* (pp. 285-289).

²³ Kadirova, N. A. (2020). UZBEK NATIONAL CHILDRENS CLOTHING AND ITS EVOLUTION. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (6), 155-157.

8. Мадумарова Зиёдахон. (2022). ЯНГИЛАНАЁТГАН ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА ГЕНДЕР МУАММОЛАРИНИ БАРТАРАФ ЭТИШДА АХЛОҚИЙ ҚАДРИЯТЛАРНИНГ ЎРНИ. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6569712>
9. Nasriddinovich, A. A. (2020). THE FEATURES OF APPEARING FAMILY IN MODERN SOCIETY. European science review, (3-4), 69-72.
10. Jamoliddinovich, U. B. (2022). FUNDAMENTALS OF EDUCATION QUALITY IN HIGHER EDUCATION. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(01), 149-151.
11. Gafurovna, R. Z. (2021). Translation Theory: Object of Research and Methods of Analysis. International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies, 24(2), 35-40.
12. Najmutdinova, D. K., Nurmukhamedova, L. S., Alieva, D. A., Maksudova, D. S., & Nosirova, Z. A. (2016). Study of the effects of the age at menopause and duration of menopause on bone mineral density in postmenopausal women in Uzbekistan. International Journal of Biomedicine, 6(1), 38-40.
13. Pulatova Sabina. (2022). THE REVELATION OF VIRTUE THROUGH EVIL IN THE SHORT STORY "A FRIEND IN NEED" BY WILLIAM SOMERSET MAUGHAM. Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnali, 1(2), 240–244. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/100>
14. Temirovna, M. P. (2021). THE CORRELATION OF HISTORICAL TRUTH AND IMAGINATION IN CHRISTOPHER MARLOWE'S TRAGEDY "TAMBURLAINE THE GREAT". Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal, 2(12), 455-457.
15. Muradovich, R. M. (2021). The Image of a Woman in The Work of Uzbek Writers. Eurasian Research Bulletin, 3, 7-12.
16. Махмурова, М., Абдуллаева, Л. С., & Самадова, С. А. Современные методы преподавания иностранных языков. Коммуникативный метод. Наука. Мысль, 6, 72-76.
17. Turaeva, K., & Zarinabonu, A. (2022). Interpretation Of Woman Image in Modern Uzbek Literature (Based on Utkir Khashimov's Book "Between Two Doors"). Eurasian Research Bulletin, 4, 42-44.
18. Вахронова Matluba. (2022). RUHIY KASALLIKLARNING INGLIZ ADABIYOTIDA BERILISHI. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6509637>

19. Oripova Kamola. (2022). O'ZBEK VA FRANSUZ TILLARIDAGI MAQOLLARDA JON KONSEPTINING IFODALANISHI. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal*, 1(3), 398-408. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/209>
20. Тухтаева, Ф. И., & Ҳамроева, Ш. Ш. (2019). Сопоставление диккенсовской концепции детства и концепции детства в произведениях Достоевского. *Мировая наука*, (5), 709-713.
21. Суяров, З. Э. (2021). СОЦИАЛЬНО-ФИЛОСОФСКОЕ ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ БЕДНОСТИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(12), 1175-1182.
22. NARZIYEVA, I. Z. (2021, March). COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE CULTURAL AND NATIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF MODERN UNITS OF ORAL SPEECH (based on Uzbek and English language materials). In *E-Conference Globe* (pp. 285-289).
23. Kadirova, N. A. (2020). UZBEK NATIONAL CHILDRENS CLOTHING AND ITS EVOLUTION. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (6), 155-157.